

ADAPTATION OF THE SHORT SENSORY PROFILE-2 (SSP-2) ASSESSMENT TOOL INTO TURKISH

¹**Meral DEVECİ**, Asistant Professor Dr

¹Tekirdağ Namık Kemal University/Vocational School of Health Services Child Development Program, 59030, Süleymanpaşa/ Tekirdağ, Türkiye
ORCID 0000-0003-1432-8544

²**Zülfiye Gül ERCAN**, Prof. Dr

²Trakya University/Faculty of Education/Elementary Education Department, 22030, Edirne, Türkiye
ORCID 0000-0002-7532-5251

¹ **Aylin YALÇIN IRMAK** Assoc. Prof.

¹Tekirdağ Namık Kemal University / Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Nursing, 59030,Süleymanpaşa/ Tekirdağ, Türkiye
ORCID 0000-0002-5879-4363

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

Meral DEVECİ

Tekirdağ Namık Kemal University/Vocational School of Health Services Child Development Program, 59030, Süleymanpaşa/ Tekirdağ, Türkiye

Abstrac—

Purpose

This study aimed to adapt the Short Sensory Profile-2 (SSP-2) to Turkish and to examine the validity and reliability of the Turkish version (SSP-2/TR) in assessing sensory processing characteristics.

Method

Study group consisted of 889 children aged 3–14 years and 11 months, 547 typically developing children, 103 children diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), and 239 children with various disabilities. In reliability analyses, internal consistency and test-retest correlations were used; in content validity, the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) was used; in criterion validity, Pearson correlation was used; and in construct validity, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used.

Results

Cronbach's Alpha values for the sub-dimensions of SSP-2/TR varied between 0.81 and 0.90 and showed a high level of internal consistency. Test-retest correlations were between 0.79 and 0.85 and were significant. The scale had acceptable fit indices. A negative, significant, and moderate correlation was found between SSP-2/TR and SSAS. In the discriminant validity analysis, a significant difference was observed between children with typical development and children with ASD.

Conclusion

SSP-2/TR can be considered a valid and reliable tool in evaluating children's sensory processing characteristics. It can be used safely in clinical and research processes by Turkish-speaking caregivers and specialists.

Keyword— Sensory processing, Psychometric properties, Cross-cultural adaptation, Validity, Reliability

1. INTRODUCTION

Sensory processing is a neurological process that enables information to be received from the environment and the body through special senses such as vision, hearing, smell, and taste, and through general/deep senses such as the tactile, vestibular, and proprioceptive senses, leading to the appropriate response to the stimulus [1]. Acquiring sensory processing is part of typical development, and this process leads to our ability to receive and interpret sensory stimuli to generate responses [2]. Regular processing contributes to the full development of motor and cognitive skills and successful participation in daily life. However, when sensory processing problems are experienced, the perception and response to stimuli differ significantly. For example, it may cause problems in daily activities and adapting to one's environment, decreased participation in school and social life [3], [2], maladaptive behaviors, attention and learning problems, and behavioral reactions [2]. It can also affect the personality [4].

Although sensory processing problems are observed to varying degrees in almost all disability groups, these problems are particularly pronounced in individuals with ASD [5]. Indeed, sensory problems are among the diagnostic criteria for ASD [6]. In addition to the assessment of sensory characteristics in ASD, the presence of sensory problems and the importance of assessing these have also been highlighted with regard to other disability groups and typically developing children [7], [3]. Studies have reported sensory problems in 92% of children with ASD, 67% of children with different special needs other than ASD [8], and 3–6.5% of typically developing children [9]. When making educational decisions about children with special needs, it is important to observe and evaluate their sensory characteristics as well as conducting screening tests for all developmental areas. Identifying sensory problems, combined with other information about the child's participation in family, school, and social activities, enables accurate determinations to be made, and the appropriate educational opportunities can be provided by modifying the environment and implementing initiatives that take into account the sensory characteristics of children and their sensory models [10].

Studies revealing the correlation between sensory processing and different areas of development also indicate that sensory processing skills are closely related to language

development, motor development, social development, and cognitive processes [11], [2], [9]. These findings reveal that sensory processing differences are not limited to sensory responses alone, but also play a decisive and multidimensional role in the child's overall developmental profile.

Given the decisive role of sensory processing in various areas of development, valid and reliable assessment tools are required in order to assess it accurately. The Sensory Profile (SP) [12] is one of the most commonly used assessment tools to assess sensory processing [9]. The Sensory Profile-2 (SP-2) [10] is a revised version of this scale and has five different forms: Infant (ISP-2), Toddler (TSP-2), Child (CSP-2), School Companion (SCSP-2), and Short Sensory Profile (SSP-2). Dunn's [12], [10] theory of sensory processing conceptually addresses an individual's strategies for perceiving stimuli (the neurological threshold) and managing them (self-regulation). According to this framework, individuals react differently according to how they perceive stimuli (at a low or high level) and how they manage them (actively or passively). These behaviors are characterized as "Seeking", "Avoiding", "Sensitivity", and "Registration" and constitute the quadrants (sub-dimensions) of the scale. These quadrants are referred to as sensory processing models [10]. The Short Sensory Profile-2 (SSP-2) was adapted from the 34 items with the highest discriminatory power in the CSP-2 [10]. The SSP-2 has been used in the literature to determine sensory profiles in ASD [13], [14], to compare the sensory models of typically developing children with disabilities other than ASD [15], and to examine the sensory processing problems of children with pediatric gastroenterology [16].

In Türkiye, the first version of the Sensory Profile (SP) [12], which was translated and adapted into Turkish by Kayıhan et al. [17], is frequently used. The SP, which is filled out by caregivers of children aged 3–10 years, consists of 125 items. It takes a long time to complete due to the high number of items and is difficult for the caregiver to answer. In the revised scale, the SSP-2, there are 34 items, which makes it more practical for caregivers to answer. It was also necessary to translate the SSP-2 into Turkish because of the increased age range covered (from 3 years to 14 years 11 months) and because the revised scale is a simple and reliable tool that provides rapid information about responses to sensory processing behavior. This study thus aimed to adapt the SSP-2 into Turkish. Thus, the SSP-2/TR will make a significant practical contribution to rapid assessment in clinical and educational settings in Türkiye and fill a gap in the literature. The scale can be used to understand the child's sensory performance and identify both their strengths and areas requiring intervention. This will contribute to the development of appropriate guidelines for interventions focused on environmental strategies.

2. METHOD

A. Design

This study had a methodological design. It was conducted in the spring semester of the 2020-2021 academic year in three provinces in Türkiye (Tekirdağ, Edirne, Kırklareli) in a primary school and special education institutions affiliated with the Ministry of National Education. The study was approved by the Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee of the relevant institution in 2020. The necessary permissions to implement the study were also obtained from the Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Türkiye. The study was carried out in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

B. Procedure

Permission was obtained from Pearson PLC, the copyright holder, for the translation and adaptation of the scale into Turkish. The translation and linguistic adaptation of the SSP-2 scale was based on the International Test Commission's (ITC's) Guidelines for Translating and Adapting Tests [Second Edition]. In adapting the SSP-2 into Turkish, the face and language validity of the scale was first conducted. The scale was translated and back-translated by

certified linguists for language validity. Items that differed between the two forms were evaluated by two Turkish language experts for their suitability to the vocabulary and structure of the Turkish language and the scale form was finalized. For content validity, the scale form was sent to 11 experts in the fields of special education, physical therapy and rehabilitation, child development and education, teaching curriculums and instruction, psychological counseling and guidance, neurology, and pediatrics. The experts were asked to evaluate the comprehensibility of the items and their appropriateness to Turkish culture on a three-point scale of “Not at all appropriate”, “Partially appropriate”, and “Fully appropriate” in order to calculate the content validity index (CVI). In line with the recommendations of the experts, minor corrections were made to the wording of some items to ensure the integrity of the meaning and simplicity of the language. The CVI value for the SSP-2/TR was 0.86 and the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) value was between 0.64 and 1. A pilot study was conducted to test the scale under real conditions and to test the comprehensibility of the items (n=15). The respondents did not report any significant problems when completing the questionnaire. The necessary information about the purpose and content of the study was provided in the institutions where permission to conduct the study had been obtained, and one caregiver from each family who volunteered to participate in the study was asked to approve the informed consent form and answer the SSP-2/TR. To assess peer validity, 87 caregivers responded to the SSAS. For test-retest reliability, 33 caregivers responded to SSP-2/TR again after 2-4 weeks.

C. Participants

This study was conducted with children aged between 3 and 14 years and 11 months who had received medical and educational diagnoses from suitably equipped hospitals and Guidance and Research Centers and who were attending special education schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education. Information regarding the children’s sensory characteristics was obtained from caregivers who were familiar with the children. No sample was selected in the study; rather, an attempt was made to reach the entire population. Participation was based on voluntariness, and data confidentiality was ensured.

A total of 889 children were included in the study. The children were divided into three groups: typically developing (n=547), children diagnosed with ASD (n=103), and children with other special needs (n=239). These other special needs included intellectual disability (n=103), attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (n=26), speech and language disorder (n=28), learning disability (n=58), and cerebral palsy (n=15). The study was conducted in the spring semester of the 2020-2021 academic year in three provinces in Türkiye (Tekirdağ, Edirne, Kırklareli) in a primary school and special education institutions affiliated with the Ministry of National Education. The inclusion criteria were that the typically developing children did not have developmental or neurological disorders, that the children with ASD or other special needs had been diagnosed at Guidance and Research Centers according to the DSM-5 criteria (Association, 2013) and were attending special education schools, and that the caregivers voluntarily agreed to participate. The exclusion criteria were being aged younger than 3 or older than 14 years and 11 months and the refusal of caregivers to participate.

D. Measures

1) *Sociodemographic Characteristics Form*: This was developed by the researchers following a review of the relevant literature. The form included the following items: Gender of the Child, Age of the Child, Child’s Disability Type, Maternal Education Level, Paternal Education Level, and Relationship of the Person Completing the Form to the Child.

2) *Short Sensory Profile-2 (SSP-2)*: This scale is a 34-item five-point Likert scale developed by Dunn [10] and designed to measure behaviors associated with abnormal responses to sensory stimuli in children between the ages of 3 and 14 years and 11 months. It is scored as “almost always” (5), “frequently” (4), “half the time” (3), “occasionally” (2), “almost never” (1), and “only when necessary”, with the sixth option of “not applicable to my child” (0). The scale, which can be applied both in print and in a web-based format, takes 5–10 minutes to complete

and consists of four quadrants (Seeking, Avoiding, Sensitivity, Registration). The Cronbach's alpha values for each quadrant were calculated as 0.80, 0.86, 0.86, and 0.79, respectively [10]. The first 14 items comprise the Sensory section, providing a general rating of how a person acts regarding sensory experiences, while the last 20 items, behavioral responses associated with sensory processing, comprise the Behavioral section. The Cronbach's alpha values of the Sensory section and the Behavioral section were calculated as 0.86 and 0.93, respectively [10]. In the scale, the sum of each quadrant score reveals the sensory behavior related to that dimension. Higher scores reflect a higher frequency of identified behaviors. For example, the higher a person's sensory sensitivity score, the more sensitive behaviors they engage in. Similarly, the higher the avoidance score, the more the child exhibits sensory avoidance behavior. In other words, a high score for each sensory dimension reveals that the behavior described within it occurs more frequently [15], [10].

3) *Social Skills Assessment Scale (SSAS)*: This scale, developed by Ataş et al. [18], is used to assess the social skills of children between the ages of 4 and 15. It is filled in by one or more family members, teachers, or other individuals who know the child well. The scale consists of 76 items and seven quadrants (Relationship Initiation and Maintenance Skills, Assertiveness Skills, Emotional Skills, Coping Skills with Aggressive Behaviors and Impulses, Problem-Solving Skills, Making Plans, Interaction with a Group, and Execution Skills). The scale items are scored on a five-point Likert scale ranging from “never” (1) to “always” (5). A high score indicates a high level of social skills. It was reported that the internal consistency coefficient for the overall total SSAS was 0.97, while for the quadrants it ranged between 0.84 and 0.92 [18]. In the present study, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the SSAS was calculated as 0.92.

4) *Statistical Analysis*: Data analysis was performed using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) 21 and AMOS package software and the results were evaluated at a 95% confidence interval and $p < 0.05$ significance level. Number, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to evaluate the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants. Item-total score correlation, internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha), and test-retest correlation were used to evaluate the reliability of the scale. The CVR was used to assess content validity, Pearson correlation was used to assess criterion validity, the student independent t-test was used to assess discriminant validity, and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used to assess construct validity. The cut-off points for the Turkish version of the SSP-2 were determined based on the bell curve. Using normative samples, the researchers determined raw scores of -2.0 and 2.0 standard deviation (SD)/Z score above and below the mean for each group and considered these points as cut-off points. Scores between -2 SD and above were considered “Much Less than Others”, scores between -2 SD and -1 SD were considered “Less than Others”, scores between -1 SD and +1 SD were considered “Just Like the Majority of Others”, scores between +1 SD and +2 SD were considered “More than Others”, and scores of +2 SD and above were considered “Much More than Others”

3. RESULTS

A. Descriptive Results

When the characteristics of the family members were examined, 84.4% of the family members who answered SSP-2/TR were the mothers of the children. Of these, 41.3% had a high school education, while 43.5% of the fathers had a high school education. Of the children in the study, 55% (n=489) were girls and 37.5% (n=333) were between the ages of 12 and 14. While 61.5% (n=547) of the children were typically developing, 11.6% (n=103) had been diagnosed with ASD and 26.9% (n=239) were children with other special needs (Table 1).

TABLE 1.
 PARTICIPANTS' CHARACTERISTICS

Characteristics		N	%
Gender of the Child	Female	489	55.0
	Male	400	45.0
Child's Age	3-5 years old	55	6.2
	6-8 years old	225	25.3
	9-11 years old	276	31.0
	12-14 years old	333	37.5
Child's Disability Type	Typically developing	547	61.5
	Autism Spectrum Disorder	103	11.6
	Other special needs	239	26.9
Maternal Education Level	Primary school	239	26.9
	High school	367	41.3
	Higher education (undergraduate)	241	27.1
	Postgraduate	42	4.7
Paternal Education Level	Primary school	202	22.7
	High school	387	43.5
	Higher education (undergraduate)	248	27.9
	Postgraduate	52	5.8
Relationship of the Person Filling Out the Form to the Child	Mother	750	84.4
	Father	114	12.8
	Other caregiver	25	2.8

B. Validity of the SSP-2

The conformity of the factor structure of the scale to the original form was evaluated using CFA. For the construct validity of the scale, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) coefficient (KMO=0.968) and the results of Bartlett's test of sphericity (17105.9; $p < .001$) were examined and it was seen that the sample was large enough and suitable for CFA. When it was examined whether the SSP-2/TR was consistent with the four quadrant structure of the original, the fit indices of the model were found to be $\chi^2=3385.93$, $p=0.00000$, $df=515$, CFI=0.97, RMSEA=0.079, NNFI=0.97, RMR=0.08, SRMR=0.04, NFI=0.97, IFI=0.97, AGFI=0.79, GFI=0.82, $\chi^2/sd=6.54$.

The CFA values of the model are presented in Figure 1 below.

$\chi^2=3385.93$, $df= 515$, $p\text{-value}=0.00000$, RMSEA = 0.079, CFI =0.97, AGFI = 0.79, GFI = 0.82, SRMR = 0.04

Fig 1.DFA Values of the Adapted Short Sensory Profile-2 Scale

C. Discriminant Validity of the SSP-2

The discriminant validity of the SSP-2 was tested by examining whether there was a difference in the total scores for the scale quadrants between the typically developing children and the children with ASD. A significant difference was found in favor of the children with ASD in all quadrants ($p < .000$) (Table 2).

TABLE 2.
 DIFFERENCE BETWEEN SSP-2/TR SCORES OF CHILDREN WITH ASD AND TYPICALLY DEVELOPING CHILDREN

Condition of the Child	Seeking (mean ± sd)	Avoiding (mean± sd)	Sensitivity (mean ± sd)	Registration (mean ± sd)
Typically developing	13.76±6.11	17.28±7.36	17.78±6.94	11.32±5.96
ASD	20.85±6.39	28.71±8.42	30.91±8.22	19.95±7.57
T Test/P value	-10.730/.000	-14.114/.000	-17.081/.000	-12.873/.000
ASD: Autism Spectrum Disorder				

D. Criterion Validity of the SSP-2

The criterion validity of the SSP-2/TR was tested by examining the correlation between the SSAS and the SSP-2 (n= 87). A negative, significant, and moderate correlation was found between the total score of the SSAS and the quadrants of the SSP-2/TR, namely Seeking (r=-.43; p<.01), Avoiding (r=-.37; p<.01), Sensitivity (r=-.44; p<.01), and Registration (r=-.39; p<.01), and the Sensory (r=-.43; p<.01) and Behavioral sections (r=-.41; p<.01). The criterion validity relationship is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3.
 CORRELATION VALUES BETWEEN THE SSAS AND SSP-2/TR

SSP-2/TR Quadrants	SSAS Total R	p	Internal Consistency	Test-Retest Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (n=33)	p
			Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient		
Seeking	-.43	.00	0.813	0.835	.000
Avoiding	-.37	.00	0.888	0.812	.000
Sensitivity	-.44	.00	0.864	0.857	.000
Registration	-.39	.00	0.880	0.798	.000
Sections					.000
Sensory	-.43	.00	0.885	.832	.000
Behavioral	-.41	.00	0.908	.791	.000

SSP-2/TR: Short Sensory Profile-2 (SSP-2) Turkish version
 SSAS: Social Skills Assessment Scale

E. Reliability of the SSP-2

The internal consistency Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the SSP-2/TR was calculated to be between 0.813 and 0.908 (Table 2). According to the test-retest correlation for the reliability of the scale, a statistically significant relationship was found between the two tests ($p < .001$). The correlation value was calculated between .791 and .857 (Table 3).

F. SSP-2/TR Cut-Off Scores

Following the guidelines for the SSP-2 [10], the cut-off points for the SSP-2/TR were determined based on the bell curve. Low raw scores represent less frequent behaviors (“Occasionally” to “Almost Never”) and are labeled "Much Less than Others" and "Less than Others". Higher raw scores, on the other hand, represent more frequent behaviors (“Frequently” to “Almost Always”) and are labeled as "More or Much More than Others". Higher scores on the SSP-2/TR were associated with more frequent behaviors, while lower scores were associated with less frequent behaviors (Table 4).

TABLE 4.

SHORT SENSORY PROFILE-2/TURKISH VERSION QUADRANT AND SECTION CUT-OFF SCORES

Quadrants	Less than Others		Just Like the Majority of Others	More than Others	
	Much Less than Others	Less than Others		More than Others	Much More than Others
Seeking (Seeker)	0-1	2-8	9-22	23-28	29-35
Avoiding (Avoider)	0-2	3-11	12-28	29-36	37-45
Sensitivity (Sensor)	0-3	4-12	13-30	31-38	39-50
Registration (Bystander)	-	0-6	7-20	21-27	28-40
Sections					
Sensory	0-6	7-23	24-58	59-76	77-100
Behavioral	0-3	4-16	17-40	41-52	53-70

4. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to adapt the SSP-2 into Turkish and to examine the psychometric properties of this adapted version (the SSP-2/TR). The sample of 889 children between the ages of 3 and 14 years and 11 months included typically developing children, children with ASD, and children with special needs other than ASD. The English version of the SSP-2 has previously been translated and adapted into Polish [19] and Persian [20].

The agreement/disagreement between the expert opinions obtained from the preliminary study on the scope validity of the SSP-2/TR scale was addressed using the CVR and CVI. The threshold value determined by Lawshe [21] as 0.59 for 11 experts was found to be between 0.64 and 1 in the present study. This showed that all items were evaluated as “completely appropriate”. The CVI value of the SSP-2/TR was found to be 0.86 and this value was above 0.80, indicating that the correlation between the scale items and the sensory features to be measured was consistent [22]. The results show that the scale was found to be appropriate by the experts in terms of content.

According to the results of CFA performed to determine construct validity, although the χ^2/df indices were not within the required ranges ($\chi^2/df = 6.54$), other fit indices were within acceptable ranges. The compatibility index that should be examined first in CFA is the χ^2/df fit statistic: a score below 3 indicates a perfect fit, and a score of 5 or below indicates a good fit [23]. However, the χ^2 test is sensitive to sample size and does not yield reliable results when the sample size exceeds 200 [24], [25]. Since the sample used in the current study was quite high, the fit value was above the threshold value. Sayın [26] examined the change in fit indices in different samples and determined that the χ^2/df value increased significantly when the number of samples increased from 250 to 500 in different models used. In the "maximum likelihood" method, which is one of the most frequently used methods in CFA, the model tested in a sample group of 250 people yielded a χ^2/df of 3.27, while it reached a value of 6.76 in a sample group of 500 people. Considering the sample size of the current study, it is considered that the χ^2/df fit index value can be safely ignored. In this case, a decision can be made by looking at other fit indices [27].

The CFI (0.97), NFI (0.97), IFI (0.97), and NNFI (0.97) values reveal that the model has perfect fit [28], [29]. The RMSEA value (0.079) shows an acceptable fit [28]. RMR (0.08) is within the acceptable limit and SRMR (0.04) indicates that the model has a high degree of fit [29]. The GFI (0.82) and AGFI (0.79) values are below 0.90. Hooper et al. [28] state that values above 0.80 are acceptable. Based on these results, when the fit indices were examined, it was concluded that the model had an acceptable and strong structural fit.

The criterion validity of the SSP-2/TR was tested by examining the correlation between the SSP-2/TR and the SSAS. In the original scale development study [10], the extent to which each social skill was exhibited was determined using the Social Skills Improvement System (SSIS) caregiver scale, and the correlation between the SSIS and the SSP-2 was examined. As a result, a significant and moderate negative correlation was determined between SSP-2 and SSIS. Since a Turkish version of the SSIS was not available, the children's social skills were evaluated by caregivers using the SSAS [18]. As in the original study, there was a significant, negative, and moderate correlation between the SSAS and SSP-2/TR quadrants. Social skills rating scales summarize positive behaviors, so negative correlations mean that social children have lower scores (experiencing fewer sensory problems) on the SSP-2 [10]. In the SSP-2/PL [19], the Social Communication Questionnaire (SCQ) was used to assess social communication problems in ASD, and the relationship between social communication symptoms in ASD and sensory processing problems was revealed. These findings indirectly confirm the validity of the measurements. In the Persian version of the SSP-2 [20], criterion validity was not evaluated.

To evaluate the discriminant validity of the SSP-2/TR, the scale scores of children with ASD and typically developing children were compared, and a significant difference was observed

between the quadrants. According to this finding, the children with ASD had more sensory processing problems than the typically developing children. In addition to sensory problems being a diagnostic criterion in ASD, studies have reported that children with ASD exhibit intense sensory processing problems, and that these problems are severe compared to their typically developing peers [5], [7], [3], [30]. Accordingly, the children with ASD had higher scores than the typically developing children, which is in line with the literature. The results of the analysis show that the SSP-2/TR has good discriminant validity.

In the reliability analysis of SSP-2/TR, the Cronbach's alpha values for the quadrants and sections were between 0.81 and 0.91, which demonstrates a high level of reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.70$). This finding proves that SSP-2/TR measures sensory properties [31], [32]. In the original version, the Cronbach's alpha values for the quadrants and sections of the scale were found to be between 0.79 and 0.93 [10], while they were between 0.71 and 0.87 in the Persian version [27]. In the Polish version of the scale, internal consistency assessments conducted separately for typically developing children and children with ASD produced results between 0.76 and 0.94 [26] in all study groups.

The test-retest of the SSP-2/TR was conducted with 33 caregivers at two to four week intervals. The test-retest method evaluates the consistency of a scale over time. If a scale is time-consistent, the scores obtained in two different measurements at different times will be highly correlated [33]. The correlation value of SSP-2/TR between the two tests was between 0.79 and 0.85 and a statistically significant correlation was found ($p < .001$). These values indicate that the scale is reliable [34], [32]. The SSP-2-PL [26] had a test repetition interval of two to four weeks and a correlation value between 0.95 and 0.98. In the Persian version of the SSP-2 [27], the retest interval was reported as being between seven and 45 days and was not reported separately as it was derived from the CSP-2 sample of the SSP-2. The CSP-2 value was found to be between 0.72 and 0.89.

The preliminary normative scores presented in this study differ from those of the original scale, and it would be appropriate to classify Turkish children according to these cut-off scores. These differences in normative values compared to the original scale are thought to stem from the scale reflecting parental perceptions as well as various cultural factors.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study is the first in Türkiye to adapt the SSP-2 into Turkish and examine its validity and reliability. The speed with which the scale can be applied, its coverage of a wide age range, and its ability to overcome the limitations of the existing long form provide significant practical contributions to clinical, educational, and research settings.

Considering all the analyses in this study, the SSP-2/TR was found to be a valid and reliable instrument for examining the sensory processing characteristics of children aged between 3 and 14 years and 11 months. The scale is a significant measurement tool that can be used by researchers and practitioners working with Turkish children. Validating and adapting the scale using a sample of children with different developmental levels is a factor that increases the practical significance of these results.

Although it was concluded that the model showed an acceptable fit in the CFA, the χ^2/df value was found to be above the threshold value accepted in the literature. Considering the sample structure and size used in the current study, the fact that the χ^2/df value exceeded the threshold value is believed to be of negligible importance. Nevertheless, different sample structures should be used in future research and the compatibility of the measurement tool should be demonstrated by repeated studies. This will allow the sample size to be determined within the framework of the number of items and the model fit to be further examined in future.

The sample used in the scale development process consisted of 547 typically developing children, 103 children with ASD, and 239 children with other special needs, for a total of 889

children. Although this sample group was entirely suitable to ensure the discriminant validity of the scale, it may have adversely affected the fit indices of the model. In future studies, a sample group consisting of children with similar characteristics may provide more evidence about the adaptation of the scale to Turkish culture.

The SSP-2/TR can be used in research and screening in Türkiye to quickly provide information about the sensory performance of the child and to identify areas of strength and areas for intervention. In addition, this tool, which can be filled in quickly and easily, can be used by individuals in a range of different professions, including, psychiatrists, psychologists and child development specialists.

6. LIMITATIONS

This study has some limitations. It was conducted in a geographic area of Türkiye commonly referred to as the "Thrace Region," which includes the provinces of Edirne, Kırklareli, and Tekirdağ. The study was also limited to the data collection processes and tools used, as well as the parents' responses to these tools, since all information about the children was obtained from their parents and could not be independently verified.

Although the large sample size is an advantage, the heterogeneous structure of the sample group and the low representation of some diagnostic groups limit the generalizability of the fit indices and validity results. Testing each diagnostic group separately with validity and reliability analyses in further studies will demonstrate that SSP-2/TR is a tool that can reliably assess sensory processing difficulties in both typically developing children and various special needs groups within Turkish culture.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Dunn, *Sensory Profile: User's Manual*, 2nd ed. San Antonio, TX: Psychological Corporation, 2007.
- [2] L. J. Miller, F. E. Anzalone, S. Lane, A. Cermak, and J. Osten, Concept evolution in sensory integration: A proposed nosology for diagnosis, *American Journal of Occupational Therapy*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 7102297010p1–7102297010p12, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5014/ajot.2017.713003>
- [3] K. Little, L. Miller, and S. T. Taylor, Sensory processing challenges and participation in school activities, *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 345–358, 2017.
- [4] Ş. Şengül-İnal and S. Sümer, Sensory processing and personality traits in adolescents, *Journal of Child and Adolescent Studies*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 112–124, 2020.
- [5] G. T. Baranek, F. J. David, M. D. Poe, W. L. Stone, and L. R. Watson, *Sensory Experiences Questionnaire: discriminating sensory features in young children with autism, developmental delays, and typical development*, *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, vol. 47, no. 6, pp. 591–601, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.2005.01546.x>
- [6] American Psychiatric Association, *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, 5th ed. Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publishing, 2013.
- [7] W. Cheung and A. Siu, *Sensory processing patterns in preschool children with developmental delays*, *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 1352–1360, 2009.
- [8] R. Green, J. Ben-Sasson, J. Soto, and C. Carter, *Sensory modulation in children with special needs: Prevalence and patterns*, *Journal of Child Neurology*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 315–322, 2016.
- [9] R. Jorquera-Cabrera, M. L. Pérez, and J. A. López, *Sensory processing in typically developing children: Prevalence study*, *International Journal of Developmental Science*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 45–53, 2017.
- [10] A. Dunn, *Sensory Profile 2: User's Manual*, San Antonio, TX: Pearson, 2014.
- [11] J. Pfeiffer, K. Koenig, and M. Kinnealey, *Effectiveness of sensory integration interventions in children with autism spectrum disorder: A pilot study*, *American Journal of Occupational Therapy*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 76–85, 2011.
- [12] A. Dunn, *Sensory Profile: User's Manual*, San Antonio, TX: Psychological Corporation, 1999.
- [13] M. Nieto, L. J. Miller, and A. Lane, *Sensory profiles of children with autism spectrum disorder: A comparative study*, *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, vol. 47, no. 10, pp. 3125–3138, 2017.
- [14] R. Simpson, S. Keen, and J. Loomes, *Short Sensory Profile in children with autism: Psychometric properties and clinical use*, *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, vol. 64, pp. 36–44, 2019.
- [15] M. Delgado-Lobete, C. Rodríguez-Bailón, and A. Molina, *Sensory processing in typically developing children compared to children with disabilities other than ASD*, *Frontiers in Pediatrics*, vol. 8, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2020.00123>
- [16] J. Wood, A. Smith, and L. Miller, *Sensory processing challenges in pediatric gastroenterology patients*, *Journal of Pediatric Gastroenterology and Nutrition*, vol. 74, no. 2, pp. 195–203, 2022.

- [17] E. Kayihan, S. Özbek, and H. Çavuşoğlu, Sensory Profile: Turkish adaptation study, *Turkish Journal of Occupational Therapy*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 15–28, 2015.
- [18] A. T. Ataş, H. İ. Efeçinar, and A. Tatar, Sosyal Beceri Değerlendirme Ölçeği'nin geliştirilmesi ve psikometrik özelliklerinin incelenmesi, *Turkish Psychological Counseling and Guidance Journal*, vol. 6, no. 46, pp. 71–85, 2016.
- [19] A. Chojnicka and W. Pisula, *Polish adaptation of the Short Sensory Profile-2: Psychometric evaluation*, *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, vol. 49, no. 7, pp. 2832–2844, 2019.
- [20] M. Shahbazi, H. Hosseini, and A. Ahmadi, *Psychometric properties of the Persian version of the Short Sensory Profile-2*, *Iranian Journal of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 210–222, 2021.
- [21] C. H. Lawshe, *A quantitative approach to content validity*, *Personnel Psychology*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 563–575, 1975.
- [22] L. Polit, C. Beck, and S. Owen, *Content validity index: A critical review of methods and reporting*, *Research in Nursing & Health*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 543–556, 2013.
- [23] R. B. Kline, *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling*, 2nd ed., New York: Guilford Press, 2005.
- [24] W. Hu and P. M. Bentler, *Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives*, *Structural Equation Modeling*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–55, 1999.
- [25] R. E. Schumacker and R. G. Lomax, *A Beginner's Guide to Structural Equation Modeling*, 4th ed., New York: Routledge, 2015.
- [26] A. Sayın, *The effect of sample size on goodness-of-fit indices in confirmatory factor analysis*, *Journal of Measurement and Evaluation in Education and Psychology*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 45–56, 2016.
- [27] B. Çokluk, E. Şekercioğlu, and Ö. Büyüköztürk, *Sosyal bilimler için çok değişkenli istatistik: SPSS ve LISREL uygulamaları*, Ankara: Pegem Akademi, 2012.
- [28] D. Hooper, J. Coughlan, and M. Mullen, *Structural equation modelling: Guidelines for determining model fit*, *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 53–60, 2008.
- [29] K. Schermelleh-Engel, H. Moosbrugger, and H. Müller, *Evaluating the fit of structural equation models: Tests of significance and descriptive goodness-of-fit measures*, *Methods of Psychological Research Online*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 23–74, 2003.
- [30] Tomchek, S. D., & Dunn, W., *Sensory processing in children with and without autism: A comparative study*, *American Journal of Occupational Therapy*, vol. 61, no. 2, pp. 190–200, 2007.
- [31] Hayran, M., *İstatistiksel yöntemler ve güvenilirlik çalışmaları*, İstanbul: Beta Yayınları, 2012.
- [32] Özdamar, K., *İstatistiksel paket programlar ile veri analizi*, 4. Baskı, Eskişehir: Kaan Kitabevi, 2004.
- [33] Best, J., *Research methods in psychology: Evaluating reliability and validity*, New York: McGraw-Hill, 2017.
- [34] Field, A., *Discovering statistics using SPSS*, 5th ed., London: Sage Publications, 2024.